

IMPROVEMENT OF INDEPENDENT CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENCY APPROACH

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Abstract. *The article is aimed at defining the stages of organization of independent creative activity of students through observation and analysis of the educational process and the organizational and pedagogical conditions for independent learning to improve the quality of the educational process. independent work instructions, development of teaching and didactic support and methods of organizing independent creative activity, as well as criteria and indicators for determining the level of improvement of independent creative activity of students on the basis of a competency approach.*

Keywords: *Competence, creative activity, independent work, independent learning, educational process, autocompetence, creative competence, independent activity. Syndicate, Project Method, Case Study.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ ТВОРЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТНОГО ПОДХОДА

Аннотация. *Статья направлена на определение этапов организации самостоятельной творческой деятельности студентов путем наблюдения и анализа образовательного процесса и организационно-педагогических условий для самостоятельного обучения с целью повышения качества образовательного процесса. инструкции по самостоятельной работе, разработка учебно-дидактического обеспечения и методов организации самостоятельной творческой деятельности, а также критериев и показателей для определения уровня совершенствования самостоятельной творческой деятельности студентов на основе компетентностного подхода.*

Ключевые слова: *компетентность, творческая деятельность, самостоятельная работа, самостоятельное обучение, образовательный процесс, автокомпетентность, творческая компетентность, самостоятельная деятельность. Синдикат, Проектный метод, Тематическое исследование.*

INTRODUCTION. The issue of continuous improvement of the educational process in the world, the development of professional training of future professionals has always been relevant. The Center for Creative Leadership Courses (IEDP, MOOC, CPC) in the most advanced educational centers of developed countries recognizes the development of creative and creative abilities of future professionals as one of the most important qualities.. The flexibility, dynamism, original creativity of professionals is important for them to adapt to new conditions and carry out innovative activities. In particular, the International Education Concept set by UNESCO until 2030 emphasizes that "quality education encourages creative thinking and

knowledge, the basics of literacy and numeracy, as well as the skills of analysis, problem solving, thinking and other interpersonal and social skills." Given

In the world, it is important to create modern teaching aids for the effective organization of the process of creative education of students through the development of creative abilities of teachers on the basis of innovative approaches such as participatory and discursive. In the world's leading universities, non-standard content and free choice of cognitive communication and creative practical actions aimed at improving the quality and effectiveness of professional training of students, as well as creative practical actions are studied as one of the factors in developing creative and communicative abilities of future teachers.

At the same time, it is important to focus on the content of education, creative thinking, the formation of practical skills, increase the share of independent study hours, the introduction of methods and technologies for independent learning. Necessary conditions are being created in Uzbekistan for the training of highly qualified specialists on the basis of international educational standards. In particular, the concept of development of the higher education system until 2030 includes "the formation of educational programs based on individual educational trajectories, the formation of creative thinking in students, the formation of practical skills in accordance with the interests of students and customer needs, the introduction of methods and technologies." to focus the learning process on the formation of practical skills"¹.

This, in addition to improving the quality of professional training of future professionals, creates the need to develop the independent creative activity of future professional education teachers in the field of higher professional education.

Today, the innovative development of scientific and technological progress, the rapid renewal of knowledge requires that future professionals quickly adapt to modern conditions and strive to acquire learning motives. This necessitates teaching students to search independently, to solve professional problems independently, to approach it creatively. Therefore, today the process of training creative, creative thinking professionals is one of the main tasks of the system of continuing education, in which the improvement of creative activity of students on the basis of a competency approach is of great scientific and practical importance.

The state educational standards provide for the implementation of teaching, educational, methodological, production, research tasks in the professional and pedagogical activities of students majoring in vocational education in the higher education system. The content of education, curriculum, science programs, forms of education, methods, tools, electronic information educational resources and other didactic materials, teaching aids and textbooks, laboratory in the formation of basic, general and special-professional competencies and the development of professional pedagogical activity in students equipment, educational technologies, etc. As a result, it is ensured that mature, qualified personnel work on their own on an independent and planned basis, consistently develop their professional and creative competencies.

The specifics of the competency-based approach to the development of independent creative and creative activities of students (future teachers of vocational education) were

¹ Incheon Declaration/Education 2030: Towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all (Word Education Forum, 19-22 may 2015, Incheon, Republic of Korea).

identified, and the essence of creative competencies and their content, approaches and their specific features were highlighted.

The above ideas, as a result of the analysis of research conducted before us, gave the following author's definition of the concept of creative activity. Creative activity is a research activity aimed at the implementation and popularization of new ideas and solutions in pedagogical collaboration. is an activity aimed at overcoming disparities and contradictions. This is the competence of creative activity according to the given definition – the concept of creating a free-creative environment in students, the establishment of an integrated learning process based on the interaction of teachers and students and the independent movement of interaction was also given a special definition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

New approaches to the organization of independent learning imply that students solve not only artificial situations, but also real practical tasks. In doing so, they learn not only from the professor, but also from each other, including working with different databases, learning to think critically and taking responsibility for the chosen solution, forming their own professional views. Theoretical analysis of the research devoted to the solution of the studied problem shows that the following approaches can be based on the organization of independent learning of students: competence, activity, systematization. Taking a look at the organization of independent work of students, its analysis shows that the changes and differences in the credit-module system with the loads in the current curriculum, in this regard, 56% of the total annual loads compared to the previous curriculum, a decrease in classroom hours, a 47% increase in total independent study, a 24% decrease in total workload, a 1008-hour difference in student leisure time in the curriculum, and an opportunity for students to work independently and creatively in the information environment. focused on the structure of education.

Modern normative documents require a new organization of the educational process, as well as independent learning of students. The State Education Standards defines a number of general competencies related to the ability of a future vocational education specialist to acquire independent learning and independent development, in particular:

1. Organize their personal activities, identify ways to solve professional problems, evaluate their effectiveness and quality.
2. Risk assessment and decision making in non-standard situations.
3. Setting and addressing professional issues, seeking, analyzing and evaluating information necessary for professional and personal development.
4. Independently identify issues of professional and personal development, engage in independent learning, consciously plan professional development [5.13.].

According to Yu.N. Kulyutkina, independent learning transfers the "professor-teacher-student" relationship from the outside to the inside. depends on the occupation [8. 48-b]. In the late 60s and 70s in western literature, in the 80s in the literature of the country a special direction by AA Binsky, E.Ya. Kogan, V.V. Laptev, O.E. Lebedev, E.A. Lenskaya and others. A competent approach to education has emerged and is being actively discussed [7]. They reflect a type of education that focuses only on learning, according to which education is intended to have a generalized experience in solving life problems, performing important tasks, social roles, competencies. From the approaches of different authors and the classification of powers, it can be concluded that powers are understood as a result of the development of abilities, which are

mainly acquired by man himself due to their practical nature, and in the future in successful interaction with others.

As a working definition of the concept of "competence" we take the definition given in the modern dictionary of vocational education, in which the concept of "competence" is defined as "the ability to apply knowledge and skills to conduct a successful work" [6. 10-b].

In the organization of independent creative activity of students on the basis of active and creative approaches: lectures (on the process of automation of technological processes) using the Project Method in practice (On the subject of practical teaching methods) design competence by teaching students to develop pedagogical software products, research projects using modern information and communication technologies in the preparation of students for professional (independent creative) activities in the educational process; use of demonstration experience in preparing students for professional activity, self-development and technical communication competence to develop students' ability to creatively study a topic (issue, problem), generalize theoretical knowledge, express ideas concisely and clearly on the basis of systematization, using the method of "Syndicate" in the seminar (Science of Educational forms reflexive competence; The research method in general education (General Sciences) has achieved the formation and development of research competencies by teaching future professionals to observe, experiment, measure, analyze, synthesize, model, automate in the educational process [13].

During the solution of the problems of pedagogical experiment, the knowledge and skills of students in the performance of creative work and laboratory work of technological-industrial description were also tested.

The following criteria were selected to assess the level of improvement of students' independent creative activity:

- cognitive criteria (knowledge and understanding);
- motivational criteria (needs and motives);
- activity criterion (application of the acquired knowledge in a concrete situation);
- reflexive (self-assessment and development of independent work).

Technologies for improving independent creative activity on the basis of a competency approach are the basis of our research, including the organization of the process of improving independent creative activity on the basis of innovative technologies ("Syndicate", Project Method, Case Study), creative exercises, problem-solving video tasks, management and outcome-based learning technologies have been developed and put into practice. Based on the methods and technologies applied in educational practice, the results of creative activity of high, middle and lower levels of motivational-value, cognitive, active and creative were analyzed as assessment criteria for determining the level of improvement of independent creative activity of students.

As a result, the formation of competent, creative professionals ready to manage professional and pedagogical processes and their readiness to meet social needs, to contribute to the development of our society is scientifically based.

Indicators of improvement of independent creative activity were assessed: high, medium and low. The following are the results of the generalized analysis of the experimental work carried out in higher education institutions in each region.

Table 1

The level of preparation of students for independent creative activity

Levels of preparation for creative activity	Experimental group				Control group			
	254 students				268 students			
	At the beginning of the experiment		At the end of the experiment		At the beginning of the experiment		At the end of the experiment	
	сопи	% да	сопи	% да	сопи	% да	сопи	% да
Past	144	56,7	93	36,8	151	56,5	139	52,0
Medium	82	32,5	104	41,0	88	33,0	97	36,3
High	28	10,8	57	22,2	29	10,5	32	11,7

The data obtained show that a low level of professional readiness was formed for 56.7% of students in the pre-experiment group, and 36.8% after the experiment. The median was 32.5 percent before the experiment, after which it showed 41.0 percent. It showed 10.8 per cent before the experiment and 22.2 per cent after the experiment. The significant dynamics of the performance of the experimental group after the experiment reflects the increase in the level of preparation of students of technical higher education institutions for creative activities.

Thus, 11.4% efficiency in education can be achieved as a result of improving the independent creative activity of students on the basis of a competency approach in the example of vocational education (Table 1).

Thus, in the educational process in the examination of pedagogical conditions for the effective operation of the model of improving the independent creative activity of students of the direction of vocational education of the technical higher education institution, in determining the results at the stages of experience detection and control, according to all selected criteria results were obtained. This is K. Pearson (χ^2) X The Xi-square was determined by quantitative analysis and comparison of control and experimental group data obtained using the statistical criterion.

DISCUSSION.

At the present stage, E.F. Zeer raises the issue of the essence of the concept, not the problem of the definition of the concept of competence, that is, “competencies today, despite many studies, are a holistic concept. In other words, the filling of the concept has not yet taken place, i.e. their psychological structure, which allows to fully understand and define competencies, has not been studied” [9. 7-p].

Within the framework of an active approach - the organization of independent education implies a change in the activities of teachers: the need to activate and transfer the student to a subjective situation, the transition from a weak consumer of information to an active participant in the educational process.

An active approach to learning involves the organization of learning activities that are gradually becoming more complex, which in turn allows for the improvement of personal qualities.

Figure 1. The structure of the interdependence of independent components in a systematic approach [3]

According to the representatives of this direction, the action approach is carried out in the context of the life of a particular learner and reflects the systemic development of the individual, that is, allows to apply the principle of systemicity in practice.

The essence of this approach is that the relatively independent components are considered to be interrelated components (Figure 1).

Figure 2. Necessary competencies and content to carry out the creative activity of a professional education teacher

The analysis of the scientific and methodological literature describes a system-activity approach, which involves the mutual integration of systemic and action approaches.

The system-activity approach is based on the theoretical principles of LS Vygotsky, P.Ya. Galperin, A.N. Leonteva, D.B. Elkonin, according to which the essence of education is the development of the individual as an element of the "being-human" system [10]. The content of education, curriculum, programs, forms of education, methods, tools and textbooks, electronic information educational resources and other didactic materials, teaching aids, laboratory equipment in the formation of basic, general and special-professional competencies in students and the development of professional pedagogical activity , based on the use of educational technologies, etc. As a result, it is ensured that mature, qualified personnel work on their own on an independent and planned basis, consistently develop their professional and creative competencies[14].

The specifics of the competency approach in the development of independent creative activity of students (future teachers of professional education) were identified, and the essence of creative competencies and their content, approaches and their specific features were highlighted.

Based on the analysis of scientific sources, the student's ability to independently manage and consciously influence the student in order to effectively use their abilities and opportunities for information and research activities, led to the conclusion that the student needs to develop the following skills:

self-motivation (to achieve goals and activate personal abilities);

independent organization of work (for work planning, organization of personal time and space, the choice of technologies and methods of solving tasks);

self-control (to monitor the progress of work and its intermediate results, to respond adequately to situations, to limit self-limitation and to refrain from unproductive actions); self-assessment (evaluation of work results) (Figure 2).

CONCLUSIONS. Thus, in the organization of independent activity on the basis of competency-based approaches, in addition to shaping the professional competencies of future professional teachers, it also encourages them to acquire the necessary competencies (social, autocompetence, extreme and special competencies) that allow them to carry out independent creative activities.

It is well known that the professional competence of a professional education teacher is different from the competence of other science teachers. Because a specialty teacher should be an expert in the relevant field as well as an educator who teaches students professional creative activity. Therefore, along with a number of professional competencies, we have identified the necessary competencies to conduct independent creative activities [12] (see Figure 2).

It is expedient to organize creative activity in the process of independent education on the basis of competent approaches in the system of higher education, to analyze their effectiveness, to study the conditions, to analyze from a scientific point of view one of the main elements of the information environment.

The issues, concepts and approaches of ensuring independent creative activity in the educational process and its implementation in the field of professional education in higher education, described in the pedagogical, educational and methodological literature on the subject

of research. Based on the analysis, the author's definition of the concept of creative activity is given: creative activity is a research activity aimed at the implementation and popularization of new ideas and solutions in pedagogical collaboration. is an activity aimed at making and testing in practice, comparing results, eliminating imbalances and contradictions in solutions.

According to this definition, the concept of competence of creative activity - the creation of a free-creative environment in students, the establishment of an integrated learning process based on the interaction of teachers and students and independent interaction [4].

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